

INSTRUCTOR GUIDE (1.1.0)

RESILIENT TECHNOLOGIES

WHY DECADES-OLD TOOLS DEFINE THE ROOT OF MODERN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

Workshop Duration: 3 hours | Format: Hands-on with live demos

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Workshop Overview

Concept: This workshop demonstrates how decades-old yet robust command-line tools can be combined into a literate programming workflow for Research Data Management (RDM). All demos use a single running use case: analysing the **NFDI Consortia Collaboration Dataset** from Zenodo.

Use Case Dataset: `Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv` – downloaded live from Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15880071](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880071)).

Narrative thread: download → clean → validate → analyse → automate → archive

3-Hour Session Plan

Time	Topic	Notes
10 min	Welcome & Context	Slides + poster overview
20 min	Emacs / org-mode (1976/2003)	Metadata, markup, org-babel, tables
15 min	curl (1997)	Download + checksum comparison
15 min	sed (1974)	In-place fix with backup
10 min	grep (1973)	Verify cleaning, complex pattern
10 min	diff (1974)	Compare original and cleaned CSV
10 min	● Break	
30 min	make (1976)	Makefile, EMACS_FLAGS, DRY principle
40 min	awk (1977)	Inline, awk block, :var, :dir/:file
10 min	tar (1979)	Archive + checksum
10 min	Wrap-up: ROOT concept	Discussion + Q&A

Before You Start – Setup Checklist

- Emacs + org-mode available (or a terminal + text editor for fallback)
- Poster PDF displayed on a secondary screen or printed for reference
- Zenodo API accessible for the curl checksum demo

Instructor Tips

- The entire workshop follows a single narrative arc: one dataset, one pipeline, many tools. Always refer back to this thread.
- Each tool section is self-contained – skip **awk** or **tar** without breaking earlier sections if time is short.
- Encourage participants to type along. Mistakes are teaching moments.
- Emphasise ROOT throughout: **R**obust, **O**pen, **O**ngoing, **T**ime-tested.

Introduction & Context --- 10 min

Open with the **Resilient Technologies** poster. Walk participants through the data-driven visualisation circle.

Talking Points

- Modern RDM relies on ever-growing platform landscapes – short life cycles, proprietary lock-in, and limited sustainability are real risks.
- Tools like Emacs, sed, awk, curl, and tar have been around for 25–50 years. They persist because of clarity, openness, and active communities.
- Today's session shows how to combine these tools in a single, reproducible pipeline – using one real dataset as the connecting thread.
- **ROOT badge:** Robust, Open, Ongoing, Time-tested – introduce now, return at the end.

► Key Points to Convey

- These tools are not relics – they are the quiet backbone of HPC clusters, data archives, and scientific workflows worldwide.
- Plain-text formats (CSV, org, Makefile) are inherently FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable.
- The goal is not to replace Python/R – it is to show what you can do *before* you even open a script.

Emacs / org-mode (1976 / 2003) --- 20 min

Planning · Production · Analysis · Archiving · Access · Re-use

Emacs is not just a text editor – it is a fully extensible research environment. **org-mode** turns plain text into a semantic markup language, task manager, analysis script, and publication tool simultaneously.

Core Message

Emacs + org-mode = a single, versionable, plain-text medium that unifies the entire research workflow. This very poster was written, executed, and typeset from one `.org` file.

Demo 1 – File Metadata / Self-Describing Document

Create a new `.org` file (`nfdi-meta-analysis.org` with `C-x C-f`) and fill it first with some metadata. Below you find an example set of metadata. Explain each keyword:

org-mode metadata

```
#+TITLE:      NFDI Analysis
#+SUBTITLE:   Collaborations of NFDI Consortia 2025
#+AUTHOR:     Lukas C. Bossert
#+DATE:       [2026-03-24]
#+EMAIL:      bossert@itc.rwth-aachen.de
#+LANGUAGE:   en
#+FILETAGS:   nfdi:coding:reproducibility
```

- These keywords drive exports (PDF/HTML/Markdown), search, and project automation.
- Because they live in plain text, they travel with the file – FAIR-friendly context without external databases.

Demo 2 – Semantic Markup

You can continue and show some of the markup possibilities in an org-mode file.

org-mode's semantic markup

```
*bold* /italics/ underline +strike-through+ ~code~ footnote:[fn]
[[https://orgmode.org][Org website]] =verbatim= [cite:@<bibtexkey>]
[[file.pdf][PDF]]
```

- Org's syntax is standardised and extensible; links have types (web, file, ID), citations integrate natively.
- The same source renders into PDF, HTML, Markdown – without rewriting.

Demo 3 – org-babel: Literate Programming

This is the key part of the workshop. Make sure you introduce it properly.

Show a live code block; execute it with `C-c C-c`. Below you find an example use. Adjust it to your needs.

org-babel code block

```
#+name: the folder structure of HOME
#+begin_src bash :eval yes :results verbatim
ls ~ | head -2
#+end_src
```

- Code, parameters, outputs, and narrative live together in one file.
- Results are cached; the entire pipeline can be re-run at any time.
- Version-controlled → auditable trail from raw data to conclusions.

Instructor Tips

You can point out that instead of writing arguments to the source block one can create a general definition for source blocks in general and for specific language source blocks.

Header commands

```
#+PROPERTY: header-args          :mkdirp yes :results verbatim
#+PROPERTY: header-args:bash     :results verbatim
```

[Optional] Demo 4 – Org Tables with Formulas

If there is time and demand, you can introduce org-mode as a way to write spreadsheets.

org-mode for spreadsheets

```
#+name: Overview of consortia and research areas
| domain | consortia | datasets | avg | % |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| Life Sciences | 8 | 123 | 15 | 13.6 |
| Humanities | 6 | 150 | 25 | 16.6 |
| Engineering Sc. | 5 | 173 | 35 | 19.1 |
| Natural Sciences | 7 | 458 | 65 | 50.7 |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| TOTAL | 26 | 904 | | |
#+TBLFM: @>$2=vsum(@2$2..@-1$2);%.0f::@>$3=vsum(@2$3..@-1$3);%.0f
#+TBLFM: @2$4..@-1$4=$3/$2;%.0f::@2$5..@-1$5=100*$3/@>$3;%.1f
```

- Tables are plain text, diff-friendly, and export to CSV/L^AT_EX/HTML.
- Recalculation is transparent – no hidden spreadsheets or manual copy-paste.

Instructor Tips

- If participants don't have Emacs, show everything from the poster PDF side-by-side. The concepts transfer to any plain-text workflow.
- The Trajan font anecdote is a good ice-breaker: even typography choices can carry the “resilience” metaphor.
- org-babel is the conceptual bridge to the rest of the workshop – everything that follows can live inside a `.org` file. (`makefile` is an exception)

Challenge 1: Your Second Literate Document (*≈5 min*)

1. Create a new file `my-meta-analysis.org` in your current working directory.
2. Add `#+TITLE:`, `#+AUTHOR:`, and `#+DATE:` metadata at the top.
3. Write a heading `* Data Overview` and a short sentence below it.
4. Insert an org-babel code block that runs `wc nfdi-analysis.org`.
5. Execute the block with `C-c C-c` and confirm the result appears as `#+RESULTS:`.

★ **Bonus:** What happens when you apply a name (`#+name: my-source`) to the org-babel source block? What is the benefit?

curl (1997) --- 15 min

Planning · Access · Re-use

`curl` is the standard tool for scriptable, reproducible data transfer. Unlike browser downloads, `curl` can be parameterised, logged, and audited – core requirements of Good Scientific Practice.

RDM Context

- Access files and metadata from repositories (Zenodo, Dataverse).
- Automate REST API queries for research data and publications.
- Validate file integrity through checksum comparison.
- Script reproducible data acquisition processes.

basic syntax

```
#+begin_src bash :eval never
curl [FLAGS] [URL]
#+end_src
```

Demo 1 – Download the File**download with progress and resume**

```
#+name: retrieve-source-file
#+begin_src bash
curl -L -O -#
↪ "https://zenodo.org/records/15880071/files/Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv" &&
↪ echo "file downloaded."
#+end_src
```

- O Save with the server's filename.
- C - Resume an interrupted download; won't overwrite existing file.
- # Show a progress bar instead of the default meter.

Take a look at the file and discuss what you can see. Here's a summary of the file:

What it is: A semicolon-delimited CSV cataloging collaborations between NFDI consortia (Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure). Each row documents a specific collaborative activity.

Structure – six columns: Type, Name, Affiliation Lead/Chair, Participating Consortia, Frequency, Output, and Status. Types of collaborations visible in the data include: Alliances – formal partnerships like Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) between consortia, joint use cases, and working groups.

Event: conference organisation: jointly organized workshops, symposia, and conferences (e.g., the NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg network meetings, deRSE sessions).

Event: conference participation: shared booths, joint posters, panel discussions at external conferences (DHd, E-Science-Tage, Love Data Week, RDA plenaries, etc.).

The file covers a wide time range, roughly 2021–2025, with many activities in 2024–2025. Statuses include completed, ongoing, and future. Dozens of NFDI consortia appear (NFDI4Chem, FAIRmat, MaRDI, DataPLANT, Text+, GHGA, NFDI4Health, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4CS, and many more), showing extensive cross-domain networking.

There's a **data quality issue** you will be fixing now in the following steps – some entries have the typo "NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk" instead of "NFDI-MatWerk."

Demo 2 – Get File Checksums

When comparing checksums of files you can make sure that the file has not been corrupted during download. That is why we compare the remote's file checksum with the local one we have downloaded before.

First you show how to retrieve the checksum of the remote file. For later we need this block being named.

query Zenodo API

```
#+name: curl-checksum
#+begin_src bash
curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" |
jq -r '.files[] | select(.key="Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv") | .checksum' |
↪ awk -F: '{print $2}'
#+end_src
```

- s Silent mode – no progress output.
- L Follow redirects (often necessary for Zenodo).

Next step is to get the checksum of the downloaded file.

checksum of local file

```
#+name: file-checksum
#+begin_src shell
md5sum Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | awk '{print $1}'
#+end_src
```

Demo 3 – Verify Integrity (Checksum Match)

Comparing the files is done using variables in the source block header. The rest is plain **bash** code.

checksum comparison

```
#+name: compare-checksums
#+begin_src bash :var remote=curl-checksum :var local=file-checksum
[[ "$remote" = "$local" ]] && echo -n "MATCH: $local" || echo "MISMATCH"
#+end_src
```

► Key Points to Convey

- The remote checksum comes from the repository metadata; the local one is computed from the downloaded file.
- A matching checksum guarantees data integrity – a key requirement of Good Scientific Practice.
- This pattern (fetch → download → verify) is the gold standard for reproducible data acquisition.

🔗 Challenge 2: Explore the Zenodo API (≈5 min)

1. Query the full metadata record and pretty-print it:

```
curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" | jq '.'
```
2. Extract just the title and publication date:

```
jq -r '.metadata.title, .metadata.publication_date'
```

★ **Bonus:** Find out how many files are attached to this record: pipe through `jq '.files | length'`

sed (1974) --- 15 min

Production

`sed` is a stream editor for transforming text – fast, scriptable, and reliable even on very large files. It excels at data cleaning: normalising metadata, harmonising formats, and fixing systematic errors.

Because transformations are declared in plain text, they are transparent, auditable, and reproducible – robust for FAIR-aligned workflows and provenance tracking.

basic syntax

```
#+begin_src bash :eval never
sed [FLAGS] 's/pattern/replacement/g' [FILE]
#+end_src
```

s Substitute: search for *pattern*, write *replacement*.

g Global flag – replace *all* matches per line.

Demo 1 – Fix a Misspelling In-Place with Backup

clean data with backup

```
#+name: sed-cleaning-delimiter
#+begin_src bash
sed -i.bak 's|NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk|NFDI-MatWerk|g' \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  && echo "file cleaned."
#+end_src
```

-i Edit the file in place (replaces the original).

.bak Creates `Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak`.

| Alternate delimiter – avoids escaping slashes in paths.

[Optional] Advanced: Regex with Capture Groups

swap two CSV fields

```
sed -E 's/^(^,+),[:,space:]*(^,+)$/\\2, \\1/' [FILE]
```

- `^...$` Anchors to the full line.
- `([^, +])` One or more non-comma characters (capture group).
- `\\2, \\1` Reinsert captured groups in reversed order.

Instructor Tips

- Always use `-i.bak` (alternatively `-i.ws` works, too) rather than raw `-i` in demos – it reinforces provenance habits.
- The alternate delimiter (`|`) is a practical tip that participants will use immediately.
- Verify right away: `ls ColL*` to show both files exist.

Challenge 3: Normalise a Second Pattern (≈5 min)

1. Check whether `NFDI4Ing` appears with alternate capitalisation using `grep -i`, then fix with `sed -i` if needed.
2. Use `sed -n` with the `p` flag to print *only* changed lines – without modifying the file.

★ **Bonus:** Chain two substitutions in one command using `-e: sed -e 's/A/B/' -e 's/C/D/'`

grep (1973) --- 10 min

Production · Analysis

`grep` – from the Unix `ed` command `g/re/p`. Extremely fast, works on arbitrarily large files, supports full regular expressions.

RDM Use Cases

- **Identifier validation** (DOIs, ORCIDs, grant IDs) and quick conformance checks on headers or required fields.
- **Quality gates** in pipelines – detect missing/forbidden values before publishing data.
- **Provenance & auditing** – save search rules and match counts alongside datasets.
- **Interoperability** in UNIX pipelines: combine with `sed`, `awk`, `sort/uniq` for reproducible, end-to-end checks.

basic syntax

```
#+begin_src bash :eval never
grep [FLAGS] PATTERN [FILE ...]
#+end_src
```

- `-i` Ignore case.
- `-v` Invert match – show lines *without* the pattern.
- `-c` Count matching lines.
- `-n` Show line numbers where matches occur.
- `-r` Search recursively through directories.
- `-E` Use extended regular expressions.

Demo 1 – Verify the sed Cleaning Worked

verify cleaning

```
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
grep -ci 'NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  || echo "file properly cleaned."
#+end_src
```

You get either a number for existing instances of the search term or: Exit code 0 from `grep` means no matches. We exploit this with `||` to print a confirmation.

Demo 2 – Filter Dataset with Complex Pattern

Next we want to apply a regex pattern. We search for each line in which `NFDI-MatWerk` is part of something that is `ongoing`. Note: here limited to the first line (`| head -1`).

complex pattern matching

```
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
grep -E "^Event:(.+?)MatWerk(.+?);ongoing$" Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head
↪ -1
#+end_src
```

^Event: Line must start with `Event:`.

(.+?)MatWerk `MatWerk` must appear somewhere in the middle.

;ongoing\$ Line must end with `;ongoing`.

► Key Points to Convey

- `grep` + regular expressions let you validate entire datasets in seconds, even at gigabyte scale.
- Combine with `-c` to get counts for reports, or redirect output to a log file for auditing.
- The same regex patterns used in `grep` can be used in `sed` and `awk` – consistency across tools.

🔑 Challenge 4: Validate and Count Your Own Consortium (≈5 min)

1. Pick any NFDI consortium (e.g. `NFDI4Chem`, `FAIRagro`, `Text+`).
2. Count how many lines mention it:
`grep -c 'YourConsortium' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv`
3. List only lines where it appears *and* the collaboration is `ongoing`.
4. Save results to `results-YourConsortium/grep-summary.txt` (create the folder first with `mkdir -p`).

Hint:

```
grep -i 'NFDI4Chem' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | grep 'ongoing'
```

diff (1974) --- 10 min

Analysis

`diff` was designed to detect line-by-line differences between text files – an idea that evolved into all modern version control systems (RCS, CVS, Git). For RDM it is the simplest yet most powerful verification tool.

RDM Use Cases

- Tracking and documenting changes in datasets, code, or metadata.
- Validating reproducibility by comparing generated outputs against references.
- Auditing transformations (e.g. after `sed` or `awk` processing).
- Verifying integrity of archived or published files.

basic syntax

```
#+begin_src bash :eval never
diff [FLAGS] [FILE1] [FILE2]
#+end_src
```

- u Unified format – 3 lines of context per change (most readable).
- q Brief – only report if files differ.
- y Side-by-side comparison.
- Un Unified format with *n* lines of context.

Demo – Compare Original and Cleaned CSV

compare files

```
#+name: diff-csv
#+begin_src bash :results output
diff -u -U0 Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak
↪ Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head -5
#+end_src
```

Expected output:

unified diff output

```
--- Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak    2025-10-21 15:51:58
+++ Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv       2025-10-21 15:52:24
@@ -11 +11 @@
-...NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk...
+...NFDI-MatWerk...
```

@@ -11 +11 @@ Line 11 in the old file was replaced by line 11 in the new.

- Lines removed from the old file.
- + Lines added to the new file.

Instructor Tips

- Emphasise: this diff output *is* the audit trail. It can be saved, versioned, and attached to a data publication.
- diff is what makes Git possible – every Git commit stores diffs under the hood.

Challenge 5: Audit Your Own Transformation (≈5 min)

1. Open the CSV in Emacs (C-x C-f), add a typo to line 5, save as `Collaboration_modified.csv` (C-x C-w).
2. Run `diff -u Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv Collaboration_modified.csv` and read the output.
3. Try `diff -q` (brief) and `diff -y` (side-by-side).
4. Save as a dated audit log: `diff -u ... > audit-$(date +%Y%m%d).patch`

Hint:

```
diff -u original.csv modified.csv > audit-$(date +%Y%m%d).patch
```

★ **Bonus:** Re-apply the patch: `patch original.csv audit-20250319.patch`. Test first with `patch --dry-run ...`

● BREAK – 10 minutes ●

make (1976) --- 30 min

Production · Analysis · Archiving

A **makefile** ties the entire workflow together: it evaluates all org-babel source blocks, writes results back into the **.org** file, and exports to one or more output formats – all with a single command. This makes the analysis fully reproducible: anyone with Emacs and **make** can regenerate every result from scratch.

makefile for the project

```
PROJECT = nfdi-analysis
EMACS ?= emacs
ORGFIL := $(PROJECT).org
SHELL := bash

# -- Export formats -----
EXPORTS += -f org-ascii-export-to-ascii # → .txt
EXPORTS += -f org-md-export-to-markdown # → .md
EXPORTS += -f org-html-export-to-html # → .html

# -- Shared Emacs flags -----
EMACS_FLAGS = -Q --batch
EMACS_FLAGS += -l org -l ob -l ob-shell -l ob-awk -l ob-org
EMACS_FLAGS += "$(ORGFIL)"
EMACS_FLAGS += --eval "(setq org-confirm-babel-evaluate nil)"

.PHONY: all execute export clean

all: execute export
@echo "* done *"

execute:
@echo "* evaluating source blocks in $(ORGFIL) *"
$(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
  --eval "(org-babel-execute-buffer)" \
  --eval "(save-buffer)"
@echo "* source blocks evaluated *"

export:
@echo "* exporting $(ORGFIL) *"
$(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
  --eval "(setq org-export-use-babel nil)" \
  --eval "(setq org-html-htmlize-output-type nil)" \
  $(EXPORTS)
@echo "* exported *"

clean:
@rm -f $(PROJECT).txt $(PROJECT).md $(PROJECT).html
@echo "* cleaned *"
```

Variables

PROJECT is the only value you ever need to change – everything else derives from it.

- =** Recursive (lazy) assignment – expanded each time the variable is used.
- ?=** Conditional assignment – only takes effect if the variable is *not* already set in your environment.
EMACS ?= emacs means you can override it without editing the file: **make EMACS=/opt/homebrew/bin/emacs**
- :=** Immediate assignment – **\$(PROJECT)** is expanded right now at parse time and stored as a fixed string.
- +=** Appends to the variable, so you can activate as many output formats as you want by simply uncommenting lines.

Export Formats

Each value is a complete Emacs command-line fragment — `-f` followed by an org export function name. All active formats are passed together to a single Emacs process and executed in sequence, producing all output files in one run.

- `-f org-ascii-export-to-ascii` Plain text `.txt`
- `-f org-md-export-to-markdown` Markdown `.md`
- `-f org-html-export-to-html` HTML `.html`
- `-f org-latex-export-to-latex` \LaTeX `.tex`

Shared Emacs Flags – DRY in Practice

Both `execute` and `export` call Emacs with the same startup flags, the same libraries, the same file, and the same initial `--eval`. Rather than writing them out twice, `EMACS_FLAGS` collects everything shared into one variable. Each target then only appends its own specific `--eval` calls.

This is the DRY principle — *Don't Repeat Yourself* — applied to a Makefile: adding a new library or changing the org filename now requires editing exactly one place.

- `-Q` **Quick start** — skip loading the user's personal init file (`~/.emacs` or `~/.emacs.d/init.el`), all site-start files, and all default customisations. This guarantees reproducible results on any machine, regardless of what packages or settings a particular user has installed. Without `-Q`, a source block might run on your laptop but fail silently on a colleague's because of a different Emacs configuration.
- `--batch` Run non-interactively and exit when done. No windows, no prompts, no GUI — output goes to the terminal.
- `-l org` Load the org-mode library.
- `-l ob` Load the org-babel dispatcher.
- `-l ob-shell -l ob-awk -l ob-org` Load the language backends explicitly. In batch mode Emacs does not auto-load these, so without them it would not know how to execute `bash`, `awk`, or `org` source blocks.
- `"$(ORGFIL)"` Pass the file as a positional argument. Emacs opens it as the current buffer, which is what `org-babel-execute-buffer` and the `-f` export functions implicitly act on.
- `--eval "...nil"` Disable the interactive confirmation prompt that org-babel shows before running code — essential in batch mode since there is nobody to click yes.

execute – Evaluate the Source Blocks

`$(EMACS_FLAGS)` expands to the full shared flag list. Two additional `--eval` calls follow:

- (org-babel-execute-buffer)** Run every source block in the file in sequence. Results are written into `#+RESULTS:` blocks inline.
- (save-buffer)** Write the updated buffer back to disk, so the `export` step that follows reads fresh results.

export – Produce the Output Files

`$(EMACS_FLAGS)` provides the shared base. Three additions follow:

- org-export-use-babel nil** Prevents org from re-executing source blocks during export. The results are already in the file from the `execute` step — no need to run everything twice.
- org-html-htmlize-output-type nil** Suppresses warnings about missing `htmlize.el`. Without this,

the HTML backend emits a warning for every code block when the library is not available in the bare `-Q` session.

\$(EXPORTS) Expands to all active `-f ...` fragments – one Emacs process, all output formats.

clean – Remove Generated Files

Removes all generated output files. The source `.org` file and any downloaded data are left untouched.

.PHONY

`.PHONY` tells `make` that these target names are not real files on disk. Without it, if a file called `clean` happened to exist in the directory, `make clean` would see it, conclude the target is already up to date, and do nothing – silently skipping the deletion.

► Key Points to Convey

- `-Q` is the key to reproducibility: stripping personal configuration means the result is identical on every machine.
- `EMACS_FLAGS` is the DRY principle in action – shared setup lives in one place; each target only adds what it specifically needs.
- `execute` runs before `export`: the `#+RESULTS:` blocks are always fresh when the document is exported.
- Activating multiple export formats costs nothing extra – one Emacs process, one run, all files.

📌 Instructor Tips

- Use `-Q` as the entry point for explaining reproducibility: *“Would this run the same way on your colleague’s laptop?”* That question frames the whole argument for batch and no-config execution.
- The `EMACS_FLAGS` refactoring is a good live coding moment – show the before (duplicated flags in both targets) and the after (shared variable) side by side so participants immediately see the value.
- If a source block fails silently in batch mode, the first debugging step is always to run it interactively in Emacs first (`C-c C-c`) and only then call `make execute`.

🔑 Challenge 6: Extend the Makefile (≈5 min)

1. Activate the Markdown export by uncommenting the relevant `EXPORTS` line and run `make` – confirm `nfdi-analysis.md` is created.
2. Add a `test` target that runs only `execute` (no export).
3. Run `make -n` to do a dry-run and observe which commands *would* execute without running them.
4. What happens when you remove `-Q` from `EMACS_FLAGS`?

★ **Bonus:** Add a `help` target that prints each available target and a one-line description using `@echo`.

awk (1977) --- 40 min

Analysis · Production

`awk` (named after its creators: Aho, Weinberger, Kernighan) combines a streaming text processor, a pattern matcher, and a lightweight programming language. It handles column-based datasets like CSV directly – bridging `grep/sed` filtering and high-level statistical scripting.

What awk can do that sed/grep cannot

- Perform real-time calculations and aggregations.
- Handle column-based datasets natively (no pre-parsing needed).
- Extract, transform, and summarise data in one pass.
- Produce structured output for further analysis or reporting.

general awk structure

```
awk -F',' 'BEGIN { init } pattern { action } END { summary }' [FILE]
```

- F','** Field separator (here , for CSV; use ; for semicolon-separated files).
- \$1,\$2** Columns/fields; **NF** = number of fields; **NR** = current record number.
- BEGIN** Initialisation block: runs once before input.
- pattern** Condition or regex tested per line: e.g. **\$3 > 0** or **/MatWerk/**.
- action** Command run when pattern matches.
- END** Finalisation block: runs once after all lines.

Demo 1 – Inline Aggregation

Running awk directly in an org-babel source block keeps code, input, and results in the same .org file.

count collaboration types (bash block)

```
#+name: awk-with-bash
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
awk -F',' ' /NFDI-MatWerk/ {cnt[$1]++; total++}
END{
  print "---- NFDI-MatWerk ----"
  for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total}' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
#+end_src
```

Demo 2 – Full Script (affiliation-count-by-type)

Now we switch from a bash-source block to an awk-source block directly.

The header arguments tell org-babel where the data comes from, what variables to pass in, and how to format the output.

awk source block

```
#+name: affiliation-count-by-type
#+begin_src awk :in-file Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var
↳ consortium="NFDI-MatWerk" :results verbatim
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}
#+end_src
```

- :in-file** Pass a file directly to the awk process as standard input – equivalent to writing the filename at the end of an awk command in the shell. The file path is relative to the .org file's directory.
- :var** Declare a named variable and its default value. Inside the awk code the variable is available by name (here: **consortium**). The value can be overridden when calling the block with **#+call**: without editing the source block itself.

:results Control how org-babel formats the output. **verbatim** inserts the raw text output as-is inside a **#+RESULTS:** block, preserving spacing and alignment. The alternative **table** would parse the output as an org table.

The variable passed via **:var** is injected by org-babel as an awk **-v** flag at runtime. The block above therefore executes as:

what org-babel runs under the hood

```
awk -v consortium="NFDI-MatWerk" '
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
```

Line by line

BEGIN { FS = ";" } Runs once before reading any input. **FS** is awk's built-in *field separator* variable. Setting it to **;"** tells awk to split each line on semicolons, so **\$1**, **\$2**, ... refer to the individual columns of the semicolon-delimited CSV.

\$0 ~ consortium The pattern tested on every line. **\$0** is awk's built-in variable for the *entire current line*. **~** is the regex-match operator – the action block only executes when the line matches **consortium**.

cnt[\$1]++ **cnt** is a user-defined *associative array* (key–value store). **\$1** is the value of the *first column* (the collaboration type, e.g. **Event: workshop**). **++** increments the counter for that key by one. If the key does not exist yet, awk initialises it to zero automatically – no explicit initialisation needed.

total++ A plain numeric variable that counts every matching line, regardless of collaboration type. Like **cnt**, it starts at zero automatically on first use.

for (t in cnt) Iterates over every key in the **cnt** array. **t** takes each key in turn (order is not guaranteed in awk). **print t, cnt[t]** outputs the type name and its count.

Data flow

The three-block structure maps directly onto the research pipeline: **BEGIN** configures the tool, the pattern–action rule accumulates data line by line (never loading the whole file into memory), and **END** produces the summary report. Because awk processes the file in a single pass, this works efficiently even on large datasets.

► Key Points to Convey

- **FS** and **\$0**, **\$1**, **\$2** ...are *built-in* awk variables – they exist automatically.
- **cnt** and **total** are *user-defined* – awk creates them on first use, initialised to zero or empty string depending on context.
- Associative arrays (**cnt[\$1]**) let you group and count by any column value in a single pass, with no **sort** or pre-processing step.
- Replacing **\$1** with **\$2**, **\$3** etc. changes which column is used as the grouping key – no other code change needed.

Demo 3 – Reuse the Block

Using **\$0 ~ consortium** instead of a hard-coded regex **/NFDI-MatWerk/** is essential: a literal regex is fixed at parse time and ignores the **:var** value entirely, whereas **\$0 ~ consortium** tests against the variable at runtime. This means swapping the consortium requires no code change – only the **:var** value:

reuse for a different consortium

```
#+call: affiliation-count-by-type(consortium="NFDI4ING")
```

Demo 4 – Write Results to a File

So far every block has written its output into the buffer as `#+RESULTS:`. For archiving and reproducibility it is often better to write results directly to a file on disk – for example to collect them later with `tar` or deposit them in a repository. Org-babel handles this entirely through header arguments: no shell redirection, no `tee`, no changes to the `awk` code itself.

write result to file

```
#+name: affiliation-count-to-file
#+begin_src awk :in-file ../Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var
↳ consortium="NFDI4Chem" :results file :dir results-NFDI4Chem :mkdirp yes :file
↳ analysis-overview.txt
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}
#+end_src
```

Four header arguments work together here:

- :results file** Instead of inserting the output into the buffer, org-babel captures stdout and writes it to a file. The `#+RESULTS:` block becomes a link to that file rather than the content itself.
- :dir results-NFDI4Chem** Sets the working directory for the block. Both the `:file` path and the `:in-file` path are resolved relative to this directory – which is why `:in-file` needs the `../` prefix to reach the CSV one level up.
- :mkdirp yes** Creates the `:dir` directory if it does not exist yet. This is what `mkdir -p` would do in a shell block.
- :file analysis-overview.txt** The filename org-babel writes to inside the `:dir` directory. The resulting full path is `results-NFDI4Chem/analysis-overview.txt`.

To run the same analysis for a different consortium, use `#+call:` and override `:dir` and the `consortium` variable at the call site – the block definition stays untouched:

reuse write-to-file for a different consortium

```
#+call: affiliation-count-to-file[:dir results-NFDI4ING](consortium="NFDI4ING")
```

Note that `:dir` and `:file` cannot reference `:var` values – header arguments are not expanded against each other in org-babel. The consortium name therefore appears twice in the `#+call:` line: once for the directory path and once as the variable value passed to `awk`. This is a known limitation; the workaround is a bash wrapper block that uses `tee` if having the name in one place matters.

 Instructor Tips

- The `#+RESULTS:` link is clickable in Emacs – press `C-c C-o` on it to open the file directly in a buffer.
- After collecting results for several consortia, the `results-*/` folders can be bundled in one step with `tar` (see the tar section) and the whole archive deposited in Zenodo.
- Show participants the folder structure with `ls results-*/` after running a few `#+call:` lines – seeing the files appear on disk makes the workflow tangible.
- Instead of a named source-block you can also do a script file approach (`awk -f`), which is better

than long inline awk for anything beyond 5 lines – easier to version-control.

- Frame awk as the bridge between grep/sed and R/Python: “before you reach for pandas, try awk”.

🔗 Challenge 7: Aggregate Your Own Consortium (≈5 min)

1. Run `affiliation-count-by-type` for NFDI4Chem by changing only the `-v` value:

```
awk -f affiliation-count-by-type \
    -v consortium=NFDI4Chem \
    Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
```

2. How many distinct collaboration types exist in the whole file? Use the hint one-liner and count the output lines.
3. Which consortium appears most often as Affiliated Lead/Chair (column 3)? Modify the one-liner to group by `$3` instead of `$1`, then pipe through `sort -t' ' -k2 -rn | head -5`.

Hint:

```
awk -F';' '{cnt[$1]++} END{for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]}' \
    Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
```

★ **Bonus:** Filter by both consortium and status: add `:var status="ongoing"` to the header and change the pattern to `$0 ~ consortium && $0 ~ status`.

tar (1979) --- 10 min

Archiving

tar – tape archive. The backbone of data packaging and long-term archiving for nearly half a century. Originally designed for magnetic tape, it remains one of the most widely used and trusted archiving tools in computing today.

RDM Value

- Platform-independent, lossless bundling of files and directories.
- Reproducible data snapshots for archiving and transfer.
- Compatible with checksums and compression utilities (gzip, bzip2, xz).
- Transparent integration in automated workflows or HPC pipelines.
- Future-proof: every UNIX-like system will unpack a `.tar.gz` even decades later.

Once all results are in place, bundle everything into a single `.tar.gz` and immediately compute a SHA-256 checksum. The `tee` command writes the checksum both to a file and to the terminal so you can confirm it at a glance.

- c** Create a new archive.
- z** Compress with gzip (`.tar.gz`).
- f** Write to the specified file.
- list** List archive contents without extracting.

Demo 1 – Archive and Checksum the Pipeline Result

create archive with checksum

```

#+name: archive-files
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
tar -czf NFDI-results.tar.gz \
  makefile *.org \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak \
  results-*/ \
  && echo "file tape-archived."
sha256sum NFDI-results.tar.gz | tee NFDI-results.tar.gz.sha256
#+end_src

```

Demo 2 – List the archived files

After archiving, always verify the contents without unpacking. `tar --list` reads only the archive header – it is instantaneous even for large archives and confirms that every expected file is present before the archive leaves your machine.

list archive

```

#+name: list-archive-files
#+begin_src bash
tar --list -f NFDI-results.tar.gz | sort
#+end_src

```

The sorted listing groups files alphabetically so you can immediately spot whether the cleaned CSV, the `.bak` provenance file, the workflow files, and all result folders are present. Anyone receiving this single `.tar.gz` can re-run the entire pipeline from scratch – the archive is a complete, self-contained research object.

► Key Points to Convey

- The `.sha256` file accompanies the archive everywhere it goes.
- The archive contains both the cleaned CSV *and* the `.bak` provenance file – a complete, self-contained research object.
- This `.tar.gz` can be deposited in Zenodo with guaranteed integrity.

👉 Challenge 8: Archive and Verify Your Results (≈5 min)

1. Create a `.tar.gz` archive:


```
tar -czf my-results.tar.gz results-YourConsortium/
```
2. Generate a SHA-256 checksum:


```
sha256sum my-results.tar.gz | tee my-results.tar.gz.sha256
```
3. List the archive contents:


```
tar --list -f my-results.tar.gz
```
4. Extract into a new folder to verify:


```
mkdir verify/ && tar -xzf my-results.tar.gz -C verify/
```
5. Compare the checksum of the re-extracted CSV with the original.

★ **Bonus:** Use `tar --exclude='*.bak'` to create a clean archive omitting backup files – useful when preparing a dataset for public deposit.

★ **Bonus:** Use `diff` from earlier to compare the files.

Wrap-Up: the ROOT Concept & Q&A --- 10 min

The ROOT Badge

Introduce ROOT as a conceptual badge applicable to all tools covered today:

R	Robust – Works reliably on huge files, across platforms, without breaking.
O	Open – Free and open-source; no vendor lock-in; community-maintained.
O	Ongoing – Actively maintained; not a relic – a living tool.
T	Time-tested – Proven over decades in real research environments.

Also Worth Mentioning (Bonus Tools)

- find (1974)** Recursively searches directory structures. Essential for navigating large research repositories.
- LaTeX (1984)** The enduring standard for scientific writing – DMPs, reports, posters, publications.
- perl (1987)** Versatile scripting for text manipulation, pattern recognition, metadata transformation.
- rsync (1996)** Synchronises and mirrors directories efficiently. Transfers only differences.
- SQLite (2000)** Serverless SQL in a single file. Excellent for metadata catalogs and portable archives.

Closing Discussion Questions

- Which of today's tools did you already know? Which surprised you?
- Where could `curl` + checksum verification replace a manual download?
- How would you add a `make` target to your next project?
- What would a “resilient” version of your own toolchain look like?

Instructor Tips

- Return to the poster wheel diagram: ask participants which phases each tool covers – this cements the big picture.
- Mention that the entire poster was generated from an `.org` file. Similar to what they've seen today – a living example of the concept.
- Leave 5 minutes for questions about the NFDI dataset itself – participants may have domain-specific follow-ups.
- Share the Zenodo DOI [10.5281/zenodo.19131603](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19131603) so participants can explore at home.

Quick Reference --- All Demo Commands

org-babel code block

```
#+name: the folder structure of HOME
#+begin_src bash :eval yes :results verbatim
ls ~ | head -2
#+end_src
```

org-mode for spreadsheets

```
#+name: Overview of consortia and research areas
| domain | consortia | datasets | avg | % |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| Life Sciences | 8 | 123 | 15 | 13.6 |
| Humanities | 6 | 150 | 25 | 16.6 |
| Engineering Sc. | 5 | 173 | 35 | 19.1 |
| Natural Sciences | 7 | 458 | 65 | 50.7 |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| TOTAL | 26 | 904 | | |
#+TBLFM: @>$2=vsum(@2$2..@-1$2);%.0f::@>$3=vsum(@2$3..@-1$3);%.0f
#+TBLFM: @2$4..@-1$4=$3/$2;%.0f::@2$5..@-1$5=100*$3/@>$3;%.1f
```

download with progress and resume

```
#+name: retrieve-source-file
#+begin_src bash
curl -L -O -#
↪ "https://zenodo.org/records/15880071/files/Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv" &&
↪ echo "file downloaded."
#+end_src
```

query Zenodo API

```
#+name: curl-checksum
#+begin_src bash
curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" |
jq -r '.files[] | select(.key="Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv") | .checksum' |
↪ awk -F: '{print $2}'
#+end_src
```

checksum of local file

```
#+name: file-checksum
#+begin_src shell
md5sum Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | awk '{print $1}'
#+end_src
```

checksum comparison

```
#+name: compare-checksums
#+begin_src bash :var remote=curl-checksum :var local=file-checksum
[[ "$remote" = "$local" ]] && echo -n "MATCH: $local" || echo "MISMATCH"
#+end_src
```

clean data with backup

```
#+name: sed-cleaning-delimiter
#+begin_src bash
sed -i.bak 's|NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk|NFDI-MatWerk|g' \
Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
&& echo "file cleaned."
#+end_src
```

verify cleaning

```

#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
grep -ci 'NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  || echo "file properly cleaned."
#+end_src

```

complex pattern matching

```

#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
grep -E "^Event:(.+?)MatWerk(.+?);ongoing$" Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head
↵ -1
#+end_src

```

compare files

```

#+name: diff-csv
#+begin_src bash :results output
diff -u -U0 Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak
↵ Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head -5
#+end_src

```

makefile for the project

```

PROJECT = nfdi-analysis
EMACS   ?= emacs
ORGFIL  := $(PROJECT).org
SHELL   := bash

# -- Export formats -----
EXPORTS += -f org-ascii-export-to-ascii # → .txt
EXPORTS += -f org-md-export-to-markdown # → .md
EXPORTS += -f org-html-export-to-html   # → .html

# -- Shared Emacs flags -----
EMACS_FLAGS = -Q --batch
EMACS_FLAGS += -l org -l ob -l ob-shell -l ob-awk -l ob-org
EMACS_FLAGS += "$(ORGFIL)"
EMACS_FLAGS += --eval "(setq org-confirm-babel-evaluate nil)"

.PHONY: all execute export clean

all: execute export
@echo "* done *"

execute:
@echo "* evaluating source blocks in $(ORGFIL) *"
$(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
  --eval "(org-babel-execute-buffer)" \
  --eval "(save-buffer)"
@echo "* source blocks evaluated *"

export:
@echo "* exporting $(ORGFIL) *"
$(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
  --eval "(setq org-export-use-babel nil)" \
  --eval "(setq org-html-htmlize-output-type nil)" \
  $(EXPORTS)
@echo "* exported *"

clean:
@rm -f $(PROJECT).txt $(PROJECT).md $(PROJECT).html
@echo "* cleaned *"

```

count collaboration types (bash block)

```

#+name: awk-with-bash
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
awk -F';' '/NFDI-MatWerk/ {cnt[$1]++; total++}
  END{
    print "---- NFDI-MatWerk ----"
    for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
    print "TOTAL:", total}' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
#+end_src

```

awk source block

```

#+name: affiliation-count-by-type
#+begin_src awk :in-file Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var
↳ consortium="NFDI-MatWerk" :results verbatim
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}
#+end_src

```

reuse for a different consortium

```

#+call: affiliation-count-by-type(consortium="NFDI4ING")

```

write result to file

```

#+name: affiliation-count-to-file
#+begin_src awk :in-file ../Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var
↳ consortium="NFDI4Chem" :results file :dir results-NFDI4Chem :mkdirp yes :file
↳ analysis-overview.txt
BEGIN { FS = ";" }
$0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
END {
  print "---- " consortium " ----"
  for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
  print "TOTAL:", total
}
#+end_src

```

reuse write-to-file for a different consortium

```

#+call: affiliation-count-to-file[:dir results-NFDI4ING](consortium="NFDI4ING")

```

create archive with checksum

```

#+name: archive-files
#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
tar -czf NFDI-results.tar.gz \
  makefile *.org \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
  Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak \
  results-*/ \
  && echo "file tape-archived."
sha256sum NFDI-results.tar.gz | tee NFDI-results.tar.gz.sha256
#+end_src

```

list archive

```

#+name: list-archive-files
#+begin_src bash
tar --list -f NFDI-results.tar.gz | sort
#+end_src

```